

Multifunctional Hybrid Composites with Gradient Interphase

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COMPOSITE APPROACHES

Micro-Reinforcement “Traditional” Approach

- GF-reinforced PP-based Composites are widely used in structural applications in the automotive industry.
- **Challenges:** High Fiber Loadings (30 – 60 wt.%), increase in density, decrease in melt flow rate (MFR), increase in brittleness, and reduced processability.

Nano-Reinforcement “Modern” Approach

- Graphene Nanoplatelets (GnPs) have exceptional mechanical, electrical, and thermal properties, allowing them to be used in a variety of industries.
- **Challenges:** Agglomerated GnPs create areas of high-stress concentration that initiate composite failure.

Hybrid-Reinforcement “Avant-garde” Approach

- **Hybrid composites** have become increasingly popular for a variety of engineering applications, due to their **enhanced properties** compared to traditional biphasic composites.
- **Significant Advantage:** Originates from the synergistic effect.

HIERARCHICAL HYBRID APPROACH

- A **hierarchically-structured** hybrid composite, consist of two reinforcing materials of **different length scales** (i.e., micro-sized and nano-sized) within one matrix material.
- The interfacial interactions between the two reinforcing materials within the hybrid composites can consist of:
 1. **Physical Interactions**
 2. **Electrostatic Interactions**
 3. **Chemical Interactions**
- Generally, **hierarchically-structured** fibrous reinforcements, that are **chemically bonded** (or **grafted**) and/or **electrostatically attached**, are known to **provide greater mechanical properties and functionalities**, compared to those that only possess physical interactions.
 - Tailoring Mechanical Performance
 - Tailoring Electrical/Thermal Conductivity Performance (EMI Shielding)

HIERARCHICAL STRUCTURE ASSEMBLY

How can we confirm Self-Assembly?

- **Electrostatic Interactions:**
 - Zeta Potential Measurements
- **Chemical Interactions:**
 - Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)
 - X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS)

Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy

Zeta-Potential

X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy

HIERARCHICAL CRYSTALLINE MICROSTRUCTURE

Effect of β -Crystal Formation

- The $(300)_\beta$ crystallographic plane is indicative of β -crystals within the crystalline microstructure.
- β -crystals provide **superior mechanical properties**: toughness, tensile strength, elongation at break, and impact strength.
- Turner-Jones et al. Method:

$$\mathcal{K}_\beta = \frac{H_{\beta(300)}}{H_{\beta(300)} + H_{\alpha(110)} + H_{\alpha(040)} + H_{\alpha(130)}} \times 100\%$$
- Biphasic PP/GF Composites**: \mathcal{K}_β is constant at $\sim 4\%$, with < 30 wt.% GF. Composites with > 30 wt.% GF decreased with increasing concentration.
- Biphasic PP/GnP Composites**: optimum formation of \mathcal{K}_β found in PPGnP0.5, maximum of 6%.
- Hybrid PP/GnP/GF Composites**: \mathcal{K}_β decreases from $\sim 16\%$ as the concentration of GF increases to $\sim 9\%$.

HIERARCHICAL CRYSTALLINE MICROSTRUCTURE

Effect of Trans-crystallization

- Crystallographic plane $(002)_{GnP}$ increases exponentially, as the GnP content increases, along with:
 - Increase in $(040)_{\alpha}$
 - Decrease in $(110)_{\alpha}$
- The promotion of **trans-crystallization** (i.e., the effect of the reinforcements to induce epitaxial growth) is quantified by:

$$I_{(040)_{\alpha}} / I_{(110)_{\alpha}}$$
 - Neat PP: **1.28**
 - PPGnP0.5: **7.92**
 - PPGF10: **1.25**
 - PPGnP0.5GF10: **3.18**
- Therefore, the successful formation of trans-crystals within the hybrid composites **promotes load transfer** from the PP matrix to the hierarchically structured reinforcement system.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES - TENSILE STRENGTH

- The Specific Tensile Strength of the **hybrid PP/GnP/GF composites**, containing ≤ 1 wt. % GnP, **perform better** than the corresponding biphasic composites with the same concentration of GF.
- An **optimum concentration** of GnP is observed in the hybrid composites with **0.5 wt. % GnP**, yielding the best tensile strengths for all concentrations of GF.
- This behaviour is attributed to the **synergistic effect** generated between the two geometrically different fillers.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES - FLEXURAL STRENGTH

- The Flexural Strength of the **hybrid PP/GnP/GF composites**, containing ≤ 1 wt. % GnP, **perform better** than the corresponding biphasic composites with the same concentration of GF.
- An **optimum concentration** of GnP is observed in the hybrid composites with **0.5 wt. % GnP**, yielding the best flexural strengths for all concentrations of GF.
- This behaviour is attributed to the **synergistic effect** generated between the two geometrically different fillers.

TENSILE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

- This Material Selection Chart compares the *Specific Tensile Modulus* versus *Specific Tensile Strength* of PP composites published in literature, to those manufactured in our laboratory.
- The experimental **hybrid PP/GnP/GF composites** have **advantageous stiffness-to-weight** and **strength-to-weight ratios**, compared to their biphasic counterparts.
- The optimum performing hybrid composite is **PPGnP0.5GF40**, with the **highest specific tensile strength**.

CONCLUSION

- The synergistic effect contributing to the enhanced mechanical properties has been attributed to:
 - The **Hierarchical Reinforcement** induces a **Gradient Interphase** that **Facilitates Load Transfer** at the interface due to the **Increased Degree of Trans-crystallization**.
 - The **Superior Crystalline Microstructure** with **Increased Crystallinity** and **β -crystal Formation**, enables the matrix to **Absorb a Substantial Amount of Energy** and **Promote Stress Transfer** to the reinforcements when exposed to strong mechanical forces.
- Primary Candidates:**
 - PPGnPO.5GF50** exceeded the flexural strength of PPGF60 by **3.3%** while providing a **9% weight reduction**.
 - PPGnPO.5GF40** obtained the same desirable flexural strength as PPGF60, while providing an **18% weight reduction**.

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